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Advancing precision livestock farming through ontology-driven interoperable health data management: Extending the Livestock Health Ontology (LHO) for enhanced disease surveillance

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Abstract:

Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) is a form of smart farming that advances agriculture by prioritizing animal care through real-time monitoring of individual animal health. Despite its potential, some challenges need attention. PLF faces challenges in integrating diverse data from different locations and formats, ensuring consistency and understanding for better animal health and welfare. To address these challenges, ontologies can play a central role. Ontologies are formal and explicit representations of knowledge that define concepts, relationships, and properties within a specific domain. In the context of PLF, ontologies serve as a structured framework, facilitating the integration and standardization of diverse data sources and ensuring a unified representation for seamless analysis and decision-making, ensuring interoperability. This paper describes Ontology-Driven Knowledge-based Farm Animal Data Management (ODKFADM) framework demonstrating a case study for the development and application of Livestock Health Ontology (LHO) by integrating AGROVOC thesauruses, specifically designed for cattle, poultry, and pigs. The aim is to enhance integration and obtain a unified view of the data for analysis and visualization. This approach focuses on resource descriptive framework (RDF) data generation, utilizing SPARQL queries for data analysis, and data visualization to enhance LHO's applications in disease surveillance and early detection. The results are served to multiple data users, and showcased via a visualization tool to provide insights to veterinarians, researchers, and farmers. In the near future, we envision that this tool, or similar ones, capture pathogen trends, provide early warnings, support informed vaccination decisions, and facilitate effective disease control on farms.

Keywords: Livestock Health Ontology, Disease Surveillance, Precision Livestock Farming, Early Detection, Infectious Diseases, Agri Semantics

1. Introduction:

The fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) introduced Agriculture 4.0 (Zhai et al., 2020), transforming farming with data-driven efficiency. Precision agriculture and digital tools improve yields (Aquilani et al., 2022) and reduce environmental impact (Symeonaki et al., 2022) by drawing insights from various data sources like sensors monitoring crops and livestock, as well as weather stations (Siebrecht, 2020). However, the diversity of data sources poses challenges due to heterogeneity in formats, schemas, and semantics. For instance, integrating farm data stored in spreadsheets, CSV files, and databases is difficult due to inconsistencies in structures and naming conventions (Thirumahal et al., 2022). Accessibility issues and meeting user preferences further complicate precision agriculture (Neethirajan & Kemp, 2021). Technical solutions must offer predictive and decision support tools with user-friendly interfaces to transform data into meaningful insights (Bahlo et al., 2019). These challenges reflect the growing demand for increased productivity, reusing the resources wisely, and manage disease outbreak effectively in Agriculture 4.0 (Symeonaki et al., 2022).

A variety of farm management systems (FMSs) or farm management information systems (FMISs) have been developed to assist farmers (Carli & Canavari, 2013; Cocca & Lindberg, 2019; Peyre et al., 2019; Siebrecht, 2020; Vasconcelos Gioia et al., 2021), focusing on tasks like data monitoring and control. However, these systems often operate as standalone applications, which can be challenging due to their tight integration with specific system specifications. Successful integrated farm management (IFM) relies on interoperability and scalability (Bhat & Huang, 2021). Intelligent systems that integrate infrastructure, technologies, applications, and stakeholders are crucial. Overcoming limitations in computation power, data storage is essential for widespread implementation of integrated precision agriculture. Semantic Web technology, including ontologies and common data representations, addresses these challenges by providing a standardized framework for organizing and describing data (Newton et al., 2020), facilitating integration and analysis for meaningful insights in PLF implementation while fulfilling the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principle guidelines (Meyer et al., 2021).

In the context of precision livestock farming, currently, numerous ontologies exist, including Animal Trait Ontology for Livestock (ATOL) (Golik et al., 2012), Infectious Disease Ontology IDO (He et al., 2021), Animal Disease Ontology ADO (Malhotra et al., 2014), Animal Health Surveillance Ontology (AHSO) (Dórea et al., 2019), Animal Health Ontology for Livestock (AHOL) (Salaun et al., 2019). These ontologies offer valuable resources for livestock management and disease surveillance. But these are too generic and upper-level. Also, these approaches do not provide a dedicated ontology focusing on disease and pathogen identification in farm animals. The AGROVOC

agriculture thesaurus (Rajbhandari & Keizer, 2012) is a linked open data for agriculture consisting of over 3200 concepts and is available in 20 different languages for public use. It serves as a valuable resource for capturing general concepts regarding agriculture and animal health. The focus of this research lies primarily on integrating the terminologies from AGROVOC due to their relevance in focusing on disease and pathogen identification in farm animals. The Livestock Health Ontology (LHO) (Noor et al., 2024) can address data heterogeneity, interoperability, and integration challenges in PLF. LHO provides a standardized framework for organizing and describing animal health data, integrating and reusing existing vocabularies like the AGROVOC thesaurus. Integrating with AGROVOC provides LHO with a rich vocabulary of agricultural concepts and its capacity for disease surveillance and early detection in farm animals. This facilitates the integration and analysis of diverse data sources to enhance disease surveillance and management in alignment with the EU objectives for data accessibility (van Schaik et al., 2023).

The key contributions of this research include setting up a standardized ODKFADM framework. Noor et al. (2024) successfully applied ODKFADM to cattle farming, and this framework is now extended to pig and poultry farming in the current paper. This extension is based on FAIR guideline principles, which enables the balancing of various factors including heterogeneous data requirements, accessibility, availability, connectivity, and value generation, enriching knowledge graphs with semantic domain knowledge for other livestock species. In this research RDF data is generated for the livestock species, utilizing the advantages of RDF for enhanced data sharing, integration, and querying capabilities. Subsequently, the RDF data was mapped to the species-specific LHO ontology to ensure semantic interoperability across different datasets. Finally, the study used data visualisation tools to facilitate precise livestock farming by providing actionable insights for disease management.

This study aims to highlight the critical importance of incorporating ontologies into PLF practices by demonstrated a case study targeting respiratory pathogens. Here, LHO enabled the integration and analysis of data from several animal health data sources, providing the structured group of data on sample types, diagnostic tests, laboratory references, geographical locations, and breed types providing a common definition of terminologies under one umbrella for each animal species (i.e. pigs, poultry, and cattle). By establishing common definitions of terminologies, LHO ensured consistency and interoperability across different data sources, facilitating the categorisation of sampling procedures and sample numbers. For example, it allows easy distinction between samples from dairy cows, beef cattle, or egg-laying poultry, and correlates this information with pathogens, diagnostic test results, and laboratory references. This integration and analysis of data using LHO provide valuable insights into the disease prevalence, transmission, and management of respiratory pathogens in livestock populations, demonstrating the effectiveness of ontologies in PLF.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data acquisition

This paper presents the ODKFADM framework as shown in Figure 1 demonstrating a case study for the development and application of LHO in livestock farming.

Figure 1: Ontology-Driven Knowledge-based Farm Animal Data Management (ODKFADM)

The framework used ontologies and RDF concepts to structure heterogeneous data. In step 1, data from various European animal health labs was collected. The datasets contain farm information in the form of CSV, excel, or pdf regarding geolocation, breed type, diagnostic tests, and pathogen identifications. The data covers 22,013 cases from year 2020 to 2024 for pigs, and 1,889 cases from year 2018 to 2022 for poultry. In step 2, the species-specific ontology, called LHO, was developed and extended. Step 3 involves integrating and mapping the RDF data from step 1 with the LHO ontology from step 2, resulting in knowledge graphs in step 4. Finally, in step 5, SPARQL queries are used to extract valuable insights regarding pathogen trends. The results of these queries can be visualized using visualization tools. Additional details regarding the visualization can be accessed in the DECIDE project's species case studies on GitHub at the following links: for poultry (<https://decide-project-eu.github.io/case-studies-website/case-studies/poultry-barometer.html>), for pigs (<https://decide-project-eu.github.io/case-studies-website/case-studies/pig-barometer.html>), and cattle (<https://decide-project-eu.github.io/case-studies-website/case-studies/cattle-barometer.html>).

2.2 RDF conversion

The algorithm in Table 1, outlines the process of converting diverse datasets into RDF format

Table 1: RDF conversion from dataset and aligned with ontology

Algorithm: Create RDF graph from dataset and aligned with ontology
<p>Input: OntologyFilePath = "path/to/your/ontology.rdf" df = pd.read_csv("path/to/your/dataset.csv") # Data Frame containing the dataset</p> <p>Output: RDFoutputFile = " path/to/your/RDFoutput.rdf"</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initialise an RDF graph: g = rdflib.Graph() 2. Define namespaces for RDF entities: Namespace = Namespace("https://www.purl.org/decide/LiveStockHealthOnto/LHO#") 3. Load the ontology into the RDF graph. g.parse(OntologyFilePath, format="xml") <p>for row_index, row in df.iterrows(): # Iterate through each row in the dataset</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Create a unique URI for the sample based on the row index. sample_uri = URIRef("https://www.purl.org/decide/LiveStockHealthOnto/LHO#Sample_" + str(row_index)) b. Add assertions for the sample, specifying its type and description. g.add((sample_uri, RDF.type, ontology.SampleClass)) description = "An individual representing a sample." g.add((sample_uri, RDFS.comment, Literal(description, lang="en"))) # Similar steps for other columns c. For each attribute in the dataset: for attribute in df.columns: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Create a unique URI for the attribute/Object property value. attribute_value_uri = URIRef("http://www.example.com/ontology#" + attribute + "_" + str(row[attribute])) ii. Add assertions for the sample having the attribute with the corresponding value. g.add((sample_uri, namespace.hasAttribute, attribute_value_uri)) g.add((attribute_value_uri, RDF.type, namespace.AttributeValueClass)) description = f"An individual representing the value {row[attribute]} for the attribute {attribute}." g.add((attribute_value_uri, RDFS.comment, Literal(description, lang="en"))) <p>g.serialise(rdf_output_file, format="xml") # Serialise the RDF graph to an output RDF file</p> <p>RDFoutputFile = " path/to/your/RDFoutput.rdf" # Output the path to the generated RDF file</p> <p>End Algorithm</p>

Mapping RDF data to the LHO involves connecting the acquired data with the categories and connections defined in the LHO, as shown in Table 2. This process is adapted to fit the unique features of each species. By matching RDF data with the ontology structure, we create a clear representation of livestock health information, making data analysis and decision-making easier.

Table 2: RDF data and ontology integration called mapping

<p>Algorithm: Load the RDF data and ontology into a panda data frame for mapping</p>
<p>Input: path_to_RDF = "output/RDFoutputCattleSampleLab1.ttl" path_to_ontology = "Ontology/LivestockHealthOnto1.0.owl"</p> <p>Output: g: The RDF graph containing both the RDF data and ontology</p> <p>Procedure: path_to_RDF = "output.rdf" <i># Define RDF data and LHO ontologypaths</i> path_to_ontology = "LivestockHealthOnto.rdf" g = Graph() <i># Create a graph object</i> g.parse(path_to_RDF, format='ttl') <i># Parse RDF file in Turtle format, add to graph</i> g.parse(path_to_ontology, format="xml") <i># Parse the ontology file and add it to the graph</i></p> <p>End Algorithm</p>

2.5 Query

The SPARQL query results highlight the potential of our approach in the field of farm animal health management. It is used to retrieve samples and associated metadata from livestock species health data with a focus on contagious respiratory diseases. A detailed discussion of query results is presented in the results section.

2.6 Visualization

To explore the knowledge graph, users can use data visualization techniques such as tableau (Daniel Heward-Mills, 2017). This allows users to explore trends, make informed decisions, and check disease outbreaks. Tableau's user-friendly interface and interactive features help efficient data analysis, researchers, veterinarians, and stakeholders.

3. Results

For demonstration purposes, a Python notebook with a small dataset of labs has been uploaded to a dedicated GitHub repository under DECIDE at <https://github.com/decide-project-eu/LivestockHealthOntologyIntegration-CattlePigPoultryUsecase->. The notebook contains the SPARQL query which retrieves samples and associated metadata from poultry, pig, and cattle health data with a focus on contagious diseases. This query enables interoperability across multiple farms, locations, and livestock species by using the SELECT clause to specify variables for retrieval and the WHERE clause to define distinct patterns for each species. The UNION operator merges these patterns into a unified result. By executing this query, the results will include samples from different labs, countries, and species, providing a comprehensive view of livestock health data in a multi-layered structure. Finally, Tableau was used to create visualizations for poultry, pigs, and cattle. It's worth noting that the tool was initially implemented successfully for cattle cases and then replicated for other species. The implementations for each species tool can be found in the DECIDE project's species case studies on GitHub at the following link: <https://decide-project-eu.github.io/case-studies-website/>. These tools focus on respiratory infectious diseases in each species in different provinces. The graphs show a positive sample percentage over time, holding the potential for early warning and supporting decision-making on farms to control infectious diseases.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we have introduced an ODKFADM framework tailored to pig and poultry health. By addressing data acquisition, integration, and analysis challenges in agriculture, we emphasize the importance of agricultural semantics. Our framework, using semantic web technologies, enhances data management, supports informed decision-making, and improves animal health outcomes. Extending the Livestock Health Ontology (LHO) with AGROVOC terminologies enriches our knowledge base, enabling effective disease surveillance. LHO ensures data consistency, integrity, interoperability, and reusability, aligned with FAIR principles. Hosting LHO on Bioportal and AgroPortal promotes utilization and community feedback. Case studies demonstrate the framework's effectiveness in pathogen trends, user feedback gathering, and impact evaluation. User-friendly visualizations like the Broiler barometer for poultry and the Pig barometer serve as valuable tools for stakeholders like veterinarians,

researchers, and farmers to monitor disease trends, allowing for early detection and informed interventions.

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